

Technology Inclusion for the Development of Small and Medium Scale Women Enterprises in Coimbatore

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Abstract

Women entrepreneurship has been recognized as an important source of economic growth. Women entrepreneurs create new jobs for themselves and others and also provide society with different solutions to management, organization and business problems. However, they still represent a minority of all entrepreneurs. Women entrepreneurs often face gender-based barriers to starting and growing their businesses, like discriminatory property, matrimonial and inheritance laws and/or cultural practices; lack of access to formal finance mechanisms; limited mobility and access to information and networks, etc. Women’s productive activities, particularly in industry, empower them economically and enable them to contribute more to overall development. Whether they are involved in small or medium scale production activities, or in the informal or formal sectors, women’s entrepreneurial activities are not only a means for economic survival but also have positive social repercussions for the women themselves and their social environment United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO, 2001). The present study is to know the level of inclusion of technology and its importance in association with socio-economic background variables.

Keywords: Women Entrepreneurship, Technology Inclusion, Increased Productivity, Profitability and Women Empowerment

Introduction

Entrepreneurship has been a male-dominated phenomenon from the very early age, but time has changed the situation and brought women as today’s most memorable and inspirational entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurship offers a greater possibility of achieving significant financial rewards than working for someone else. Female-run enterprises are steadily growing all over the world, contributing to household incomes and growth of national economies. However, women face time, human, physical, and social constraints that limit their ability to grow their businesses. Women cannot achieve true liberation without the participation and cooperation of men. Indian women are today at the cross-roads of their destiny. There is a great up-surge in consciousness about their rights among all sections and classes of society in all regions of the country. There has been a tremendous increase in development activity for women since the eighties with a great leap forward in the nineties. The country has entered the new millennium with the hope that we will achieve even greater equity in

the 21st century. "It is now accepted by' all serious social scientists that the vast majority of women have always been economically productive and that the differing degrees and differing forms of power and authority held by different classes cultures and nation depended on the historical changes in production relation. The effort of development has been both in the social and economic spheres although it is clear that more emphasis has been placed on improving the social status of women. Education makes women more skilled and informed; and property rights allow her to be a powerful participant in family decisions. Women empowerment means to treat women at equal footing and empower them with such opportunities which may bring them on par with men. Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) are engines of job creation and growth in emerging markets that are central to the larger equation of development. These dynamic, fast-moving firms make a special contribution to local economies. Increasing women's earnings is a powerful catalyst of development. It generates new capital that is often reinvested in the health, education, and well-being of families, building a future for the next generation. Even though we observe a number of women entrepreneurs in the business, recent studies show that most of them are found in Micro and Small Enterprises(MSEs).

According to World Bank (2007), entrepreneurship has the following benefits.

1. Entrepreneurs are their own bosses. They make the decisions. They choose whom to do business with and what work they will do. They decide what hours to work, as well as what to pay and whether to take vacations.
2. Entrepreneurship offers a greater possibility of achieving significant financial rewards than working for someone else.
3. It provides the ability to be involved in the total operation of the business, from concept to design and creation, from sales to business operations and customer response.
4. It offers the prestige of being the person in charge.
5. It gives an individual the opportunity to build equity, which can be kept, sold, or passed on to the next generation.
6. Entrepreneurship creates an opportunity for a person to make a contribution. Most new entrepreneurs help the local economy. A few through their innovations contribute to the society as a whole.
7. It is a catalyst for economic change and growth. Entrepreneurship increases per capital output and income. By doing so it involves initiating and constituting change in the structure of business and society. As a result entrepreneurship contributes a lot in increasing countries output and productivity
8. Entrepreneurship encourages innovation and creativity. It develops new products or service for the market to fulfill human needs. It also stimulates investment interest in the new ventures being created. Entrepreneurship through its process of innovation creates new investment of new ventures. More ventures being created, new jobs will be produced, thus reduce the unemployment rate. That will create and promote wealth distribution.

Women's productive activities, particularly in industry, empower them economically and enable them to contribute more to overall development. Whether they are involved in small or medium scale production activities, or in the informal or formal sectors, women's entrepreneurial activities are not only a means for economic survival but also have positive social repercussions for the women themselves and their social environment United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO, 2001).

Review of Literature

Gurumurthy and Chami, (2014) the report shows that the use of mobile banking technology has rapidly increased in developing countries, but evidence on its impact on women's opportunities and influence is mixed .

A study of Kabeer, N. and Natali, L. (2013) in particular, household relationships have been identified as an influential sphere of life that can have important spillover effects on women's

entrepreneurship development and all spheres of life. According to Akalp et al (2012), a growing body of research of the twenty-first century explores the characteristics, motives, leadership styles, management skills, and strategies of the female entrepreneur, documenting case studies and strategies for success. A number of researchers argue that further studies are required, but all agree that innovation or the drive for innovation is the first criteria for successful entrepreneurship, especially in developed countries.

According to Hampel - Milagrosa's study (2011) some gender differences were evident in attitudes to business. Women and men were equally likely to describe themselves as motivated to succeed in their businesses, but women were somewhat less likely than men to describe themselves as wanting employment and financial independence, being open to innovation or interested in increasing their productivity and considerably less likely to want their work to fit their family life or to believe that registering their business would benefit them.

According to Itaniet al., (2011) Personal attributes of female entrepreneurs may also sometimes create opportunities or barriers for them. There are a high proportion of females who have a fear of failure. At the other end of the spectrum, some studies reveal that female entrepreneurs love to take risk, are open to challenges, and put in their best efforts to pursue their goals (Mordiet al., 2010).

According to Nadgrodkiewicz, (2011), in lower-income classes, female entrepreneurship may be due to the need to meet family expenses, while among middle-income groups it can be attributed to the desire to raise the standard of living.

Woolley and Malone (2011) pointed out that many women entrepreneurs described building their business as building a team. They also argue that women entrepreneurs share criticism constructively, have open minds, and are not autocratic.

Itani et al, (2011) most governments are putting efforts into encouraging female entrepreneurship but many women are unaware of these schemes to promote their businesses.

Brush et al., (2010) said that the relatively high rates of women entrepreneurship in emerging and developing economies are primarily due to high levels of "necessity entrepreneurship."

Objectives

- To assess the usage of technology and its importance in manufacturing Sector.
- To find out the importance of training in usage of technology in SMEs
- To know the level of inclusion of technology in association with socio-economic background variables.

Methodology

Coimbatore is the Manchester of South India. It is the centre for the Textile and Manufacturing industry. There are 13,314 entrepreneurs in Coimbatore (source from District Industry Centre 2014-2015) out of which 2449 women are entrepreneurs in Coimbatore, out of which 281 women are focusing exclusively in manufacturing sector. According to the Krejcie & Morgan table (1970) 162 respondents were selected randomly. Five data were excluded due to improper information. The study is descriptive in nature. The participants responded on a 5-point Likert-type scale, anchored by Strongly Agree (5 point) and Strongly Disagree (1 point) for each item. Tools used for data collection is based on review of literature. The collected data was analyzed using SPSS.

Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1 Analysis of Variance

Variables	Groups	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Age	Between Groups	3.540	3	1.180	2.216	.089
	Within Groups	81.479	153	.533		
	Groups	85.019	156			
	Total					
Marital Status	Between Groups	4.209	3	1.403	2.657	.050
	Within Groups	80.810	153	.528		
	Groups	85.019	157			
	Total					
Education	Between Groups	1.248	4	.312	.566	.688
	Within Groups	83.771	152	.551		
	Groups	85.019	156			
	Total					
Family type	Between Groups	.244	1	.244	.446	.505
	Within Groups	84.775	155	.547		
	Groups	85.019	156			
	Total					
Experience in SME	Between Groups	3.819	4	.955	1.787	.134
	Within Groups	81.200	152	.534		
	Groups	85.019	156			
	Total					
Nature of the Organization	Between Groups	7.041	4	1.760	3.431	.010
	Within Groups	77.978	152	.513		
	Groups	85.019	156			
	Total					
Organization Deals with	Between Groups	14.801	5	2.960	6.366	.000
	Within Groups	70.218	151	.465		
	Groups	85.019	156			
	Total					

The above table 1 shows that, marital status, nature of organization and organization deals with various goods has significant difference within and between groups whereas age, education, family type and experience in SME have no significance.

Table 2
Chi-Square test

Variables	Technological inclusion in SMEs
Age	.063
Marital Status	.055
Education	.872
Family type	.375
Experience in SME	.100
Nature of Organization	.006
Organization deals with various goods	.001

As observed from the above table 2, nature of organization and organization deals with various goods has significant positive effect on technological inclusion in manufacturing sector of SMEs whereas age, marital status, education and family type do have significant effect.

Table 3

Technological inclusion in small medium scale industries	Percentage
Low (up to 55)	20.4
Moderate (56 to 63)	43.3
High (64 and above)	36.3
Total	100.0

As observed from the above table 3, the inclusion of technology in small and medium scale enterprises in the manufacturing sector of women entrepreneurs in Coimbatore was at moderate level.

Conclusion

The present study states that, the inclusion of technology in small and medium scale enterprises in the manufacturing sector of women entrepreneurs in Coimbatore was at moderate level. This brings the necessity to make the women entrepreneur to understand that inclusion of technology in various forms and process in the manufacturing sector could enable increase in productivity per unit input with less labour and manual work force. On the other hand technology will provide better quality in the production process and enable consistency in product supply and marketing.

The 'F' test result shows that, marital status, nature of organization and organization deals with various goods has significant difference within and between groups whereas age, education, family type and experience in SME have no significance.

The chi-square findings shows that, nature of organization and organization deals with various goods has significant positive effect on technological inclusion in manufacturing sector of SMEs whereas age, marital status, education and family type do have significant effect.

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